

**MEMORIES OF MAQSUD SHAYKHZODA N. FROM THE BOOK
"MAQSUD SHAYKHZADEH" BY KARIMOV**

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Annotation: about the life and work of Maqsud Shaykhzoda, about his entry into Uzbekistan and acquaintance with the famous writers here, about his creations during the war years. His works embody the floral echo of a burning soul, which lived with great revolutionary ideals, vivid patriotic feelings, truly creative emotions

Keywords: Maqsud Shaykhzadeh, life, creativity, famous, writers, creativity, works, great, patriotic.

On the occasion of the day the master poet was born, Naim Karimov's "Maqsud Shaikhzoda" is from the memories that have taken place from the book.

There will be such creators who, even after their deaths, will forever live in the memory of the people, not only with their works, which are located in the treasury of national literature, but also with their amazing human qualities and bright images. One such Creator is Maqsud Shaykhzadeh.

Born in the homeland of Nizami, Shaikhzoda came to Uzbek soil with the flange of Falak and lived the happy and tragic days of his life here. Here he formed as a poet, playwright, literary scholar, translator and educator, making a huge contribution to the development of Uzbek literature, literary studies and the translation school.

The new educational novel by the famous literary scholar Naim Karimov is devoted to the arduous fate of the Sheikhzoda, which tells about the life of the poet on the basis of memories of contemporaries and secret documents.

I knew the honorable Mukhtar Avezov from 1928. In the same year, Maqsud Shaykhzoda, Subutoy Dolimov, Viktor Reshetov, Nodirkhan Nazarov, Sherbek Aliev, several other guys and girls entered the Oriental Faculty of the Central Asian State University. Since some of us are still grotesque teenagers who have graduated from the land of knowledge and the rest of us have graduated from various techniques, we need a coach with excellent intelligence, rich in life experience.

Such a coach that we dreamed of was found in our faculty. We were attracted by the light of love, when a young middle-aged man, barvasta, red as if he did not get

two Beti patterns, with his eyes narrowed, and a Kazakh-like middle-aged man, splashed on his cheek. Did not Youth leave interest, or did some force take us to its magic, in any case we became interested in that person and began to question who he was. But we did not have time to inquire, but the man himself came to ask us. He introduced himself to us in a gentle, sweet dialect, where his tone was felt, so that we entered our higher educational institution, welcomed the descent of Science, and his native language was Kazakh. It was clear that the good fortune of that man had overtaken us. That's why, we couldn't talk to him, opening up and spreading. We decided a talk, a land, a blush, a buzzer. Why would we lose ourselves until the head of the head fell on our eyes to the black hair of TIM, an antique tie neatly tied on the collar of a white jacket with no Ogori shedding, a handsome black suit made of English shevyote. But this lying did not go far. The scourge of love of the autonomous Agha has warmed us. We now began to look at that person as our close mouth, liver, and most importantly, coach.

One day, the autonomous Agha, talking to all of us, suddenly stared at the sheikhdom. The man was seen somewhere with Maqsud, at some point-it seemed that he could not be tossed.

-Did I see you, boy? he said, " O Muhammad!

Maqsud became as strange as the one who was at a disadvantage. But a sharp mind worked that could save him from any Musk:

- You saw here, autonomous Aga, here, " he replied.

- Not a surprise. But I seem to have seen you a lot, even spoken.

The Mukhtar Agha said something as if he were talking to himself, and he was again staring at Maqsud. This time he became like the one who made a pact to check the face lines of The Sheik. So tightly sewed. Then face-with a cute smile that brightens his eyes:

- Where Are you, my Beaver? - he said.

Shaikhzoda stood out from all of us not only in the sense of reason, but also in the sense of siymo. The idle question of the autonomous mouth did not seem to melt into it. On the contrary, everywhere, all the time, in all environments and conditions, the feeling of pride, which has made his heart prosperous, has been exasperated. He leaned, even proud, and said that he was Azerbaijani, coming from Azerbaijan. While reciting the same words, Maqsud's face seemed as if the sun in the sky had moved.

In this way, a thread of intimacy was tied between these two objects of the future.

This little dialogue left a strong taasurot in us, especially in me, which will not be forgotten for life. Autonomous Oga U Mahal must be between thirty and forty years old. He used the words in his place, the treatment in place, and with his deep meditation and discussions, he absorbed the person. After that brief communication, which filled our hearts with the charms of love, we became the most cherished, the most loving Agha, who was often seen with the autonomous Agha, even when they saw it, and rejoiced as if they were seen with the most loving Agha. Above the head of the head, the head swam, and the eyes of the head smiled, there was a world of generosity, Mehru compassion, which seemed to palm the dignity of man.

I still remember that one unpleasant incident hurt the autonomous mouth. What caused one of the students who enrolled at the same time as us to drop out. When Mukhtar Agha heard this, he was deeply moved, as if his own son had left. For a few days, he could not swallow the pain inside, and his eyelids went unopened. It was in a beautiful three-story brick building on the present Leningrad8 street of our faculty. One day, when we were going to bed after class, the aliono became an autonomous Aga. We were talking on the road. But there was maleness in what he said, and tenderness in his heart. Alien to the nature of the autonomous mouth it became quickly known that the boy of the tund. The talk turned around and came to a child who had abandoned that reading.

- Chakki! He did a very bad job, " said The Mukhtar Agha, sighing deeply.

That's what we said. A spark of joy flashed in that person's thoughtful eyes. Worried that we would not be left one after another, haligi opened his face from what we said.

Full of hardship with the hardships of reading, learning, learning, learning, days followed by days, months after months passed.

In the same pressing days of study, Maqsud Shaikhzoda's Tobi escaped. As a result of the accident, he did not come to study for several days. The two sheets of the autonomous mouth, which always blush like no pattern, suddenly turned white. It was the face-slapping of anxiety inside. We both went to the flame market and took wet fruit, sedan Obi bread, allusions again. Mukhtar Agha was a high-minded person who enjoyed praising the qualities of people. For this, the roadside praised and described the good quality and qualities of the Sheikha.

- Look at me, Mirzakalon, which one day the professors sat down talking and told a strange saying about Maqsud. When they finish their lectures and ask if there is

a question, Maqsud would not give their questions orally, fill out one or even two pages of the notebook and give them in writing. Is that true?

Was true. He always asked his questions not verbally, but in writing. I confirmed. The headman thought like a man standing in front of a puzzle. The trick turned to me after thinking:

— Why didn't you know what it was like? "he asked.

- I found out. I asked himself, " I said.

- What did he say?

- In the world there is a word “maybe”. This cannot be overlooked. Did you avoid the review, after all, one day gives a Pand. Suppose our domain could not immediately answer the question. Can it be so? You can, of course. Then there will be domla Izza, who could not answer the student's question. I will write down my questions for the possibility of such a “possibility”.

- Abbo, Azamat-O! - sent Mukhtar Aga.

In those clefts, the Shaikhzoda stood in an old house in the Kashgar neighborhood. He saw an autonomous mouth and stood up, as if he had found an ointment for pain. These two objects of the perspective were chewed in their own language, like two birds that only they understand. It really went about literature, art, science and science.

Soon after that, Mukhtar Aga left for Moscow⁹.

Many years passed between the same tahlid. This, full of hard work and the hard work of creativity, made the autonomous Agha one of the great masters of the East pens, while Maqsud Shaykhzadeh was also the author of a number of philosophical poetic works, lifelong dramas, master of the Munavvar translation – a great literary Mudarri, raising both to the rank of famous people of this world.

LITERATURE USED

1. Mamurova, F. I. (2021, May). ARTIST OF UZBEKISTAN MAKSUD SHEIKHZADE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 176-178).
2. Mamurova, F. I., & ugli Abdubahabov, A. A. (2023). TWO FOLK POETS. “TRENDS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND PRACTICE”, 1(3), 23-30.
3. Islomovna, M. F., & Abduvoxob o’g’li, A. A. (2023, January). Maqsud Shayxzodaning Hayoti Va Ijodi. In Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences (USA) (pp. 19-20).
4. Mamurova, F. I. (2021, May). ARTIST OF UZBEKISTAN MAKSUD SHEIKHZADE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 176-178).

5. Islamovna, Mamurova Feruza. "MAQSUD SHAYKHZADEH-TWO FOLK DILBANDI." INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGY AND LINGUISTICS. Vol. 1. No. 1. 2024.
6. Islamovna, M. F. (2024, January). MAQSUD SHAYKHZADEH-TWO FOLK DILBANDI. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGY AND LINGUISTICS (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 189-192).
7. Islomovna, M. F. (2024). O 'ZBEK ADABIYOTINING ATOQLI NAMOYANDALARIDAN BIRI MAQSUD SHAYXZODNING "JALOLIDDIN MANGUBERDI" ASARI. Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi, 2(1), 89-92.
8. Islamovna, M. F. (2024). THE CREATION OF MAQSUD SHAYKHZODA-AS A GOLDEN LEGACY. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 2(1), 90-93.
9. Mamurova, F., & Ataxanov, O. (2024). MAQSUD SHAYXZODA HAYOTI HAQIDA. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(10), 111-116.
10. Mamurova, Feruza, and Durdona Obutjonova. "DESCRIBING MAKSUD SHAIKZODA." Current approaches and new research in modern sciences 3.4 (2024): 5-8.
11. Obutjonova, D. (2024). O'ZBEK VA OZARBAJON XALQINING SEVIMLI SHOIRI. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(10), 103-105.